

Comparative Evaluation of Generative Augmentation Techniques for Imbalanced Concrete Damage Segmentation: Classical Methods, GANs, and Diffusion Models

Kalyan Khatri

^aUniversity of New Haven, 300 Boston Post Road, West Haven, 06516, Connecticut, USA

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ABSTRACT

Automated segmentation of concrete surface damage has been a persistent challenge in structural health monitoring, and the difficulty is not purely a modelling problem. Real-world inspection imagery is severely imbalanced, with damaged pixels representing cracking, spalling, corrosion, and exposed reinforcement bar accounting for as little as 0.27% of image area. While data augmentation is a widely adopted strategy for addressing this imbalance, no controlled study has directly compared classical, generative adversarial, and diffusion-based augmentation strategies on a structural damage dataset under identical experimental conditions. This study presents the comparative study of augmentation strategies for concrete damage segmentation on the MDMCS/HRCDS benchmark dataset with 1,200 high-resolution RGB inspection images annotated across four different damage categories. A standard U-Net backbone is trained under identical conditions across four different strategies: a raw imbalanced baseline, classical augmentation, pix2pix conditional GAN augmentation, and mask-conditioned generation using zero-shot ControlNet with Stable Diffusion 1.5. Generation quality is assessed via Fréchet Inception Distance alongside downstream per-class Dice coefficient, mean Intersection-over-Union, and Precision-Recall AUC on a held-out test set. Contrary to prevailing assumptions, the raw baseline achieved the highest mIoU (0.721) and mean Dice (0.836), outperforming all augmentation strategies. Among generative approaches, pix2pix GAN augmentation achieved the highest crack Dice (0.869) despite severe mode collapse (FID=334.71), while ControlNet diffusion augmentation (FID=176.25) demonstrated superior training regularization without surpassing the baseline. An ablation study further reveals that LoRA fine-tuning on N=1,000 images does not improve generation quality as FID remained stable at approximately 177 across zero-shot, 15-epoch, and 40-epoch configurations suggesting that small-dataset fine-tuning corrupts pretrained diffusion representations. These results suggest that loss function design outweighs augmentation strategy for small structural inspection datasets, and that FID does not reliably predict downstream segmentation improvement.

1. Introduction

Infrastructure deterioration is a growing concern worldwide. Concrete structures like bridges, tunnels, retaining walls, and building facades degrade over time through cracking, spalling, corrosion of embedded reinforcement, and progressive exposure of rebar. Left undetected, these damage forms compromise structural integrity and, in severe cases, lead to catastrophic failure. Traditional inspection relies on trained engineers conducting manual visual inspections which is slow, expensive, and subject to human errors Kim and Cho (2020); Arafin, Billah and Issa (2024).

The automation of visual inspection through deep learning-based image segmentation has emerged as a promising direction. Convolutional neural networks, and more recently transformer architectures, have demonstrated strong performance on benchmark structural damage datasets Khatri, Elmi and Samsami (2026); Hu, Ma and Xiao (2024). Yet a fundamental data problem exists in real inspection imagery, damaged regions occupy a small fraction of the total image area. A wall with a hairline crack is predominantly undamaged concrete. A bridge deck showing early-stage spalling still presents mostly intact surface. This pixel-level imbalance where damage classes accounts for less than one percent of image area creates training conditions that standard segmentation pipelines are not designed to handle.

Data augmentation is one of the commonly adopted technique to class imbalance and limited dataset size in image segmentation. By generating the training distribution through geometric transforms or synthetic image generation,

 kalyankhatri@outlook.com (K. Khatri)

 <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-1943-1680> (K. Khatri)

ORCID(s):

augmentation strategies aim to expose the model to a broader range of damage appearances and improve minority class representation. In structural inspection specifically, where annotated datasets rarely exceed a few thousand images, augmentation is often applied as a default pre-processing step with limited justification for the specific strategy chosen Dunphy, Fekri, Grolinger and Sadhu (2022).

The landscape of augmentation has expanded considerably in recent years. Classical approaches like flipping, rotation, brightness adjustment, and noise injection remain widely used. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), particularly the pix2pix conditional framework Isola, Zhu, Zhou and Efros (2017), have been applied to synthesise paired image-mask training samples in domains where real data is scarce. More recently, diffusion models like ControlNet have been used on semantic layouts Zhang, Rao and Agrawala (2023) which has demonstrated remarkable image synthesis quality on natural image benchmarks, prompting interest in their application to domain-specific inspection datasets. Despite this growing toolkit, no study has evaluated all three augmentation techniques side by side on the same structural damage dataset under controlled and reproducible conditions.

This study addresses that gap using the MDMCS/HRCDS concrete inspection benchmark, where four training strategies on a standard U-Net segmentation backbone under strictly identical conditions are evaluated. The four strategies are: (1) a raw imbalanced baseline with no augmentation, (2) classical geometric and photometric augmentation via the Albumentations library, (3) conditional image synthesis using a pix2pix generative adversarial network trained on mask-image pairs, and (4) mask-conditioned image generation using zero-shot ControlNet with Stable Diffusion 1.5.

The principal contributions of this work are as follows:

1. A controlled four-way comparison of augmentation strategies on the MDMCS/HRCDS structural damage benchmark under identical experimental conditions, providing the first systematic evidence of relative augmentation effectiveness for concrete damage segmentation.
2. Quantitative demonstration that inverse-frequency class weighting combined with a joint Cross-Entropy Dice loss produces a stronger segmentation baseline (mIoU = 0.721) than any augmentation strategy evaluated including generative approaches trained on 2,000 image-mask pairs.
3. Evidence that pix2pix GAN augmentation achieves competitive crack segmentation performance (Dice = 0.869) despite severe mode collapse showed by FID of 334.71, suggesting that spatially correct damage layout contributes to downstream segmentation independently of photorealistic texture synthesis.
4. An ablation study demonstrating that LoRA fine-tuning of Stable Diffusion 1.5 on datasets of 1,000 images does not improve generation quality indicating that small-dataset fine-tuning corrupts pretrained diffusion representations rather than adapting them.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on concrete damage segmentation, class imbalance handling, and generative augmentation. Section 3 describes the MDMCS/HRCDS dataset and the annotation processing pipeline. Section 4 details the experimental methodology. Section 5 presents quantitative and qualitative results across all four strategies. Section 6 discusses the implications of the findings with practical recommendations. Section 7 discusses the limitation of this study, and Section 8 concludes .

2. Related Work

2.1. Concrete Damage Segmentation

Visual inspection of concrete infrastructure has a long history of manual practice, but the limitations of human-based assessment have driven sustained interest in automated alternatives. Early computer vision approaches relied on handcrafted features and threshold-based methods to detect surface cracks, but these techniques struggled with the visual variability of real inspection environments (Munawar, Hammad, Haddad, Soares and Waller, 2021).

The introduction of convolutional neural networks transformed the field. Fully convolutional architectures, particularly U Net (Ronneberger, Fischer and Brox, 2015), became a dominant framework for pixel-level damage segmentation due to its encoder-decoder structure and skip connections, which preserve spatial detail critical for detecting fine damage features (Arafin et al., 2024). Subsequent work extended segmentation to multiple simultaneous damage categories. Kim and Cho (Kim and Cho, 2020) demonstrated instance segmentation of four concurrent damage types (cracking, efflorescence, rebar exposure, and spalling) using Mask R-CNN on a dataset of 765 annotated concrete images, reporting precision and recall above 87% for segmentation. More recently, transformer based architectures have been applied to structural damage detection, with Hu et al. (Hu et al., 2024) proposing a Graph Feature Refinement

approach within a Transformer framework that achieved damage identification accuracy of 96.71% on benchmark structural data.

Despite these advances, a persistent challenge remains largely unaddressed in the literature: the severe pixel-level class imbalance inherent to concrete inspection imagery. Most studies either report results on datasets where damage classes are relatively balanced, or apply standard augmentation without explicitly measuring its effect on minority class performance (Dunphy et al., 2022). Our own prior work on UAV-based bridge deck inspection (Khatry et al., 2026) encountered this limitation directly, motivating the systematic investigation presented here.

2.2. Class Imbalance in Segmentation

Class imbalance is one of the challenge in semantic segmentation, where the unequal distribution of pixel-level class frequencies causes standard training objectives to implicitly favour majority classes. In the context of concrete inspection, this problem is particularly acute: background pixels dominate by a wide margin, and minority damage classes such as cracking can occupy less than one percent of the total image area (Dunphy et al., 2022).

Several strategies have been proposed to address this imbalance at the loss function level. The Dice loss, introduced for volumetric medical image segmentation by Milletari et al. (Milletari, Navab and Ahmadi, 2016), directly optimises the overlap between predicted and ground truth regions rather than pixel-wise accuracy, making it inherently more sensitive to minority class performance. Focal loss (Lin, Goyal, Girshick, He and Dollár, 2017) addresses the imbalance problem by down-weighting the contribution of well-classified easy examples, forcing the model to focus on hard minority class pixels during training. Class-weighted cross-entropy, in which loss contributions are scaled inversely to class frequency, remains one of the most straightforward and widely adopted approaches for handling imbalanced segmentation tasks (Tauzowski, Ostrowski, Bogucki, Jarosik and Błachowski, 2025; Jing, Ma, Zhang, Wang, Huang, Xu and Zhang, 2025).

In structural damage applications, these strategies are rarely compared systematically. Most existing studies either adopt a single loss function or treat class imbalance as a secondary concern addressed through augmentation rather than through loss design. This study takes a different approach: the combined Cross-Entropy Dice loss with inverse-frequency class weighting is treated as the primary mechanism for handling imbalance, with augmentation strategies evaluated against this well-tuned baseline rather than against a naive training setup. This design choice establishes a stronger reference condition than is typical in the augmentation literature.

2.3. Classical Augmentation

Classical augmentation uses a broad set of transformations applied directly to training images and their corresponding annotations. Geometric transforms including horizontal and vertical flipping, rotation, scaling, and affine distortion simulate variability in camera angle and inspection distance. Photometric transforms such as brightness and contrast adjustment, gamma correction, hue and saturation shifts, and additive noise simulate variation in lighting conditions, surface weathering, and sensor characteristics. Together these transforms are intended to reduce overfitting and improve model generalization by exposing the network to a broader range of plausible input conditions (Buslaev, Iglovikov, Khvedchenya, Parinov, Druzhinin and Kalinin, 2020).

In the structural inspection domain, classical augmentation is nearly universal. Studies applying deep learning to crack detection, spalling segmentation, and multi-class damage assessment includes flipping, rotation, and brightness adjustment as standard preprocessing steps (Dunphy et al., 2022; Arafin et al., 2024; Khatry et al., 2026). However, the assumption underlying these transforms does not hold equally for all damage classes. Thin linear structures such as cracks are particularly sensitive to geometric distortion: rotation and affine transforms alter the apparent orientation and continuity of crack morphology in ways that may not reflect naturally occurring crack patterns in inspection imagery (Jing et al., 2025).

The CoarseDropout regularisation technique, which randomly masks rectangular regions of the training image, has been proposed as a complementary approach to force the model to rely on contextual rather than purely local texture features (Buslaev et al., 2020). This is particularly relevant for structural damage segmentation, where local texture can vary across inspection sites and lighting conditions. Despite the widespread use of classical augmentation in this domain, systematic evaluation of whether these transforms actually improve minority class performance rather than simply improving overall accuracy on majority classes remains largely absent (Dunphy et al., 2022).

2.4. GAN-based Augmentation

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), introduced by Goodfellow et al. (Goodfellow, Pouget-Abadie, Mirza, Xu, Warde-Farley, Ozair, Courville and Bengio, 2014), offer an alternative to deterministic augmentation by learning to

synthesise realistic images from the training distribution. The conditional variant, pix2pix (Isola et al., 2017), extends this framework to paired image translation tasks by learning a mapping from a conditioning input to a target output. Applied to structural damage augmentation, pix2pix is trained on mask-image pairs such that a segmentation mask is used as input and a realistic damage photograph is produced as output, providing synthetic training samples with guaranteed spatial correspondence between image and annotation.

GAN-based augmentation has seen growing application in domains where annotated data is scarce. In structural health monitoring, Dunphy et al. (Dunphy et al., 2022) applied GAN-based generation to expand imbalanced structural damage datasets, reporting improved classification performance on minority damage classes. Similar approaches have been explored in medical image segmentation, where conditional GANs have been used to generate synthetic lesion images for underrepresented classes (Yi, Walia and Babyn, 2019). The common premise across these applications is that GAN-generated images, by capturing the statistical structure of real training data, provide more semantically meaningful augmentation than geometric transforms applied to existing samples.

However, GAN-based augmentation carries well-documented risks on small datasets. Mode collapse, in which the generator converges to a limited subset of the target distribution rather than its full diversity, is a persistent failure mode that becomes more likely as dataset size decreases (Goodfellow et al., 2014). On datasets of fewer than a few thousand images, the discriminator can memorise the training distribution, destabilising the adversarial training dynamic and producing degenerate outputs. Despite these known risks, most existing studies apply GAN augmentation without quantifying generation quality through metrics such as Fréchet Inception Distance (Heusel, Ramsauer, Unterthiner, Nessler and Hochreiter, 2017), making it difficult to assess whether improved downstream performance is attributable to genuine distributional coverage or to incidental regularization effects. This study addresses that gap by reporting FID alongside segmentation metrics for both GAN and diffusion augmentation strategies.

2.5. Diffusion Model Augmentation

Denoising diffusion probabilistic models have emerged as a powerful alternative to GANs for image synthesis, offering more stable training dynamics and superior coverage of the target distribution (Rombach, Blattmann, Lorenz, Esser and Ommer, 2022). Unlike GANs which learn through adversarial competition, diffusion models learn to reverse a gradual noising process, iteratively denoising random noise into realistic images conditioned on text prompts or spatial inputs. Stable Diffusion (Rombach et al., 2022) extends this framework to operate in a compressed latent space, substantially reducing computational requirements while maintaining high synthesis quality.

ControlNet (Zhang et al., 2023) introduced a mechanism for adding spatial conditioning to pretrained diffusion models without modifying the base model weights. By attaching trainable copies of the encoder layers conditioned on spatial inputs, ControlNet enables precise spatial control over the generated output. Applied to structural damage augmentation, a segmentation mask can be used as the conditioning signal, guiding the diffusion process to generate realistic concrete inspection images whose damage regions correspond to the mask layout.

Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) (Hu, Shen, Wallis, Allen-Zhu, Li, Wang, Wang, Chen et al., 2022) provides a parameter-efficient mechanism for fine-tuning large pretrained models on domain-specific datasets. Rather than updating all model weights, LoRA introduces small trainable rank-decomposition matrices into the attention layers, adapting the model's output distribution toward the target domain while preserving the broader pretrained knowledge. In this study, LoRA fine-tuning of the Stable Diffusion UNet on concrete inspection images was evaluated as a domain adaptation strategy prior to synthetic image generation.

The application of diffusion models to structural inspection augmentation remains relatively underexplored. Most existing work applies diffusion augmentation to natural image or medical imaging benchmarks where large training datasets are available (Yi et al., 2019). The behaviour of diffusion-based augmentation on small domain-specific datasets has not been systematically studied. This study contributes direct evidence on this question through a controlled ablation comparing zero-shot, 15-epoch, and 40-epoch LoRA configurations on a dataset of 1,000 concrete inspection images.

3. Dataset

3.1. Dataset Description

Experiments were conducted on the MDMCS benchmark (Guo, Jiang, Meng and Bao, 2026), a publicly available concrete inspection dataset hosted on Mendeley Data. The dataset comprises 1,200 high-resolution RGB images of reinforced concrete surfaces collected from real inspection sites, annotated across four damage categories: cracking,

Table 1

Pixel-level class distribution across the MDMCS training set (1,000 images). Frequencies are computed from single-channel segmentation masks prior to any augmentation.

Class	Pixel Count	Frequency (%)	Inv. Weight
Background	610,908,523	78.56	0.28
Spalling	141,096,233	18.15	1.21
Corrosion	11,265,213	1.45	15.21
Exposed Rebar	12,213,748	1.57	14.03
Crack	2,116,283	0.27	81.56

spalling, corrosion, and exposed reinforcement bar. Images were provided in pre-defined training, validation, and test splits of 1,000, 100, and 100 images respectively.

The dataset was selected for three reasons. First, its scale is representative of real structural inspection datasets, which are inherently limited by the cost and access constraints of annotated field data. Second, it covers four damage categories that span a range of visual characteristics: cracking presents as thin linear structures, spalling as large irregular surface loss, corrosion as diffuse staining with distinctive colour signature, and exposed rebar as elongated metallic structures within spalled regions. Third, the dataset shows the pixel-level class imbalance that motivates this study making it a realistic and challenging benchmark for evaluating augmentation strategies under conditions that reflect actual deployment scenarios.

All images were resized to 512×512 pixels for model training. Annotations were provided in LabelMe format as per-image JSON files containing polygon vertices for each damage instance. Prior to training, these annotations were converted to single-channel segmentation masks with pixel values encoding class identity: 0 for background, 1 for crack, 2 for spalling, 3 for corrosion, and 4 for exposed rebar. Polygon rasterisation was performed using the Python Imaging Library, with overlapping polygons resolved by assigning priority to the class with the largest pixel count in the overlapping region.

3.2. Class Imbalance Analysis

A defining characteristic of the MDMCS dataset is the severe pixel-level class imbalance between background and damage categories. To quantify this imbalance, pixel frequencies were computed across all 1,000 training images by summing per-class pixel counts from the generated segmentation masks. The results are summarised in Table 1.

The background class dominates the training distribution, accounting for 78.56% of all labelled pixels. Among damage categories, spalling is the most prevalent at 18.15%, reflecting its characteristic appearance as large contiguous surface regions. Corrosion and exposed rebar occupy comparable proportions at 1.45% and 1.57% respectively. Cracking is the most severely underrepresented class at 0.27% yielding a background-to-crack pixel ratio of approximately 289:1. This ratio represents one of the most extreme class imbalance conditions reported in the structural damage segmentation literature, and poses a direct challenge to standard training objectives that optimize pixel-wise accuracy without accounting for class frequency.

To address this imbalance at the loss function level, inverse-frequency class weights were computed from the training set pixel distribution and applied to the cross-entropy component of the combined training loss. The weight for class c is defined as:

$$w_c = \frac{1/f_c}{\sum_{k=0}^{C-1} 1/f_k} \cdot C \quad (1)$$

where f_c denotes the pixel frequency of class c in the training set and $C = 5$ is the total number of classes. The resulting weights, shown in the final column of Table 1, assign a weight of 81.56 to the crack class. This weighting scheme ensures that the loss function penalizes misclassifications of minority damage pixels proportionally to their scarcity, providing the model with an explicit signal to attend to rare damage categories during training.

Figure 1 illustrates the pixel frequency distribution across classes on a logarithmic scale, highlighting the multi-order-of-magnitude difference between background and crack class representation.

4. Methodology

4.1. Segmentation Backbone

All four experimental strategies share a common segmentation backbone, a standard U-Net architecture (Ronneberger et al., 2015) with base channel width of 64. The encoder consists of five successive stages: an initial double convolution block followed by four downsampling stages, each comprising a 2×2 max-pooling operation and a double convolution block. Each double convolution block applies two sequential 3×3 convolutions with batch normalisation and ReLU activation. The decoder mirrors the encoder through four upsampling stages, each using bilinear interpolation followed by concatenation with the corresponding encoder skip connection and a double convolution block. A final 1×1 convolution maps the decoder output to a five-class logit map.

The channel progression through the network is 64, 128, 256, 512, and 1024 in the encoder bottleneck. The total parameter count is 31,385,093. All input images are resized to 512×512 pixels and normalised using ImageNet statistics (mean [0.485, 0.456, 0.406], standard deviation [0.229, 0.224, 0.225]) prior to inference. The output logit map is passed through a softmax function to produce per-class probability maps, and the predicted class for each pixel is determined by

$$\hat{y} = \arg \max_c p_c(x)$$

where $p_c(x)$ denotes the predicted probability of class c at pixel x .

The U-Net backbone was selected for three reasons. First, its encoder-decoder structure with skip connections is particularly well-suited to segmentation tasks requiring both global context and fine spatial detail. Second, its relatively modest parameter count makes it trainable from scratch on datasets of 1,000 images without prohibitive overfitting risk. Third, its widespread adoption in structural damage segmentation literature provides a meaningful reference point for comparing our results against prior work (Arafin et al., 2024; Kim and Cho, 2020).

4.2. Loss Function

Training employs a combined loss function that addresses pixel-level class imbalance through two complementary mechanisms: class-weighted cross-entropy and soft multi-class Dice loss. The combined loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \alpha \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{Dice}} \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha = 0.5$ assigns equal weight to both components. This balance was fixed across all four experimental strategies to ensure that loss function design does not confound the comparison of augmentation strategies.

4.2.1. Class-Weighted Cross-Entropy Loss

The cross-entropy component penalises pixel-wise misclassification with class weights derived from the training set pixel distribution as defined in Equation 1. For a pixel x with ground truth class y and predicted probability vector $\mathbf{p}(x)$, the weighted cross-entropy loss is:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{x=1}^N w_{y_x} \log p_{y_x}(x) \quad (3)$$

where N is the total number of pixels in the batch, y_x is the ground truth class at pixel x , $p_{y_x}(x)$ is the predicted probability for the ground truth class, and w_{y_x} is the inverse-frequency weight for that class as defined in Equation 1. The weight assigned to the crack class (81.56) is approximately 292 times that of the background class (0.28), directly counteracting the 289:1 pixel ratio between these classes.

4.2.2. Soft Dice Loss

The Dice loss component directly optimizes the overlap between predicted and ground truth segmentation regions, making it inherently robust to class imbalance (Milletari et al., 2016). For multi-class segmentation, the soft Dice loss is computed independently for each foreground class and averaged:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Dice}} = 1 - \frac{1}{C-1} \sum_{c=1}^{C-1} \frac{2 \sum_x p_c(x) g_c(x) + \epsilon}{\sum_x p_c(x) + \sum_x g_c(x) + \epsilon} \quad (4)$$

where $C = 5$ is the total number of classes, $p_c(x)$ is the predicted probability of class c at pixel x , $g_c(x) \in \{0, 1\}$ is the ground truth indicator for class c at pixel x , and $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$ is a smoothing constant to prevent division by zero. The background class ($c = 0$) is excluded from the Dice computation to prevent the dominant background class from masking the loss signal from minority damage classes.

The combined loss thus operates on two parallel levels: the cross-entropy component provides stable pixel-wise gradient signal scaled by class frequency, while the Dice component directly maximizes segmentation overlap for each damage category independently of its pixel prevalence. Together they address the 289:1 background-to-crack imbalance more effectively than either component alone (Jing et al., 2025).

4.3. Training Protocol

An identical training protocol was applied across all four experiments. This controlled setup ensures that observed differences in segmentation performance are attributable to the augmentation strategy rather than to variation in optimization conditions, architecture, or evaluation procedure.

4.3.1. Optimizer and Scheduler

Model parameters were optimized using the Adam optimizer (Kingma and Ba, 2014) with an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-4} and weight decay of 1×10^{-5} . The learning rate was annealed using a cosine schedule:

$$\eta_t = \eta_{\min} + \frac{1}{2}(\eta_0 - \eta_{\min}) \left(1 + \cos \left(\frac{t}{T_{\max}} \pi \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

where $\eta_0 = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ is the initial learning rate, $\eta_{\min} = 1 \times 10^{-6}$ is the minimum learning rate, t is the current epoch, and $T_{\max} = 60$ is the total number of scheduled epochs. Gradient norms were clipped to a maximum of 1.0 to prevent gradient explosion during early training epochs. Mixed precision training was enabled using PyTorch Automatic Mixed Precision (AMP) with `float16` compute and `float32` master weights, reducing GPU memory consumption without affecting convergence behaviour.

4.3.2. Training Configuration

All models were trained for a maximum of 60 epochs with a batch size of 8 and input resolution of 512×512 pixels. Early stopping was applied with a patience of 12 epochs monitoring validation mIoU and training was terminated if no improvement greater than $\delta = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ was observed over 12 consecutive epochs. The model checkpoint achieving the highest validation mIoU was retained for test set evaluation. All experiments were conducted on a single NVIDIA A100 GPU via Google Colaboratory Pro.

4.3.3. Data Loading

Training images and their corresponding segmentation masks were loaded as matched pairs. For experiments involving synthetic augmentation, real and synthetic datasets were combined using a concatenated DataLoader with uniform sampling. Validation and test evaluation used only real images in all four strategies to ensure that performance metrics reflect generalization to true inspection imagery rather than synthetic distribution coverage. The complete training configuration is summarized in Table 2.

4.4. Strategy 1: Baseline (Raw Imbalanced)

The baseline strategy applies no data augmentation beyond ImageNet normalization. Training images are loaded, resized to 512×512 pixels, and normalized using the mean and standard deviation values described in Section 4.1. No transforms are applied during training. This strategy establishes the reference condition against which all augmentation strategies are evaluated.

The baseline is not a naive training setup. The combined Cross-Entropy Dice loss with inverse-frequency class weighting described in Section 4.2 is applied in full. This design is deliberate: it isolates the contribution of augmentation from the contribution of loss function design, allowing the two to be evaluated independently. A baseline that already incorporates best-practice loss function design provides a more meaningful reference condition than one that uses a naive unweighted cross-entropy loss.

The training set for the baseline consists of 1,000 real image-mask pairs from the MDMCS training split. No synthetic images are added. The model is trained for up to 60 epochs with early stopping as described in Section 4.3, and the checkpoint achieving the highest validation mIoU is retained for evaluation.

Table 2

Training hyperparameters applied identically across all four experimental strategies.

Hyperparameter	Value
Optimiser	Adam
Learning rate	1×10^{-4}
Weight decay	1×10^{-5}
LR scheduler	CosineAnnealingLR
Min. LR	1×10^{-6}
Batch size	8
Max epochs	60
Early stopping	Patience = 12
Min. delta	1×10^{-4}
Input resolution	512×512
Precision	AMP float16
Gradient clipping	Max norm = 1.0
GPU	NVIDIA A100

4.5. Strategy 2: Classical Augmentation

The classical augmentation strategy applies geometric and photometric transforms to each training image and its corresponding segmentation mask during data loading. Transforms are applied stochastically at each training step using the Albumentations library (Buslaev et al., 2020), ensuring that the model encounters a different augmented view of each image at each epoch rather than a fixed pre-generated augmented dataset.

4.5.1. Geometric Transforms

Four geometric transform groups were applied. Spatial flipping was applied independently in the horizontal and vertical directions, each with a probability of 0.5. Random 90 rotation was applied with probability 0.5. Affine distortion was applied with probability 0.5. All geometric transforms were applied identically to both the image and its segmentation mask to preserve spatial correspondence between input and annotation.

4.5.2. Photometric Transforms

Five photometric transform groups were applied to the image only as segmentation masks are invariant to colour and intensity changes and were passed through unmodified. Random brightness and contrast adjustment (limits ± 0.2) was applied with probability 0.5. Random gamma correction (range 80-120) was applied with probability 0.3. Hue, saturation, and value shifts (limits ± 20 , ± 30 , ± 20 respectively) were applied with probability 0.3. JPEG compression simulation (quality range 70-100) was applied with probability 0.2 to simulate compression artifacts common in field-collected inspection imagery. Gaussian noise injection (variance range 10-50) was applied with probability 0.2.

4.5.3. Regularization

CoarseDropout was applied with probability 0.3, randomly masking between 1 and 8 rectangular regions of 32-64 pixels per side. This regularization technique forces the model to rely on contextual features rather than localized texture patterns, which is particularly relevant for concrete inspection where surface texture varies substantially across inspection sites (Buslaev et al., 2020). Following all stochastic transforms, images were normalized using ImageNet statistics and converted to tensors.

The training set for Strategy 2 consists of the same 1,000 real image-mask pairs used in the baseline, with augmentation applied on-the-fly during training.

4.6. Strategy 3: pix2pix GAN Augmentation

The third strategy augments the training set with synthetic image-mask pairs generated by a pix2pix conditional GAN (Isola et al., 2017) trained on the MDMCS training split. The GAN learns a direct mapping from segmentation masks to photorealistic concrete inspection images, enabling the generation of synthetic training samples with guaranteed spatial correspondence between damage layout and image appearance.

4.6.1. GAN Architecture

The pix2pix framework comprises a U-Net generator and a PatchGAN discriminator (Isola et al., 2017). The generator follows an encoder-decoder structure with skip connections, taking a colour-coded segmentation mask as input and producing a 512×512 RGB image as output. The discriminator operates on overlapping 70×70 image patches, classifying each patch as real or generated rather than making a single global judgement.

4.6.2. Training

The GAN was trained for 200 epochs on the 1,000 mask-image pairs of the MDMCS training split using a combined adversarial and pixel-wise L1 loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{pix2pix}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{cGAN}}(G, D) + \lambda \cdot \mathcal{L}_{L1}(G) \quad (6)$$

where G and D denote the generator and discriminator respectively, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{cGAN}}$ is the conditional adversarial loss, \mathcal{L}_{L1} is the pixel-wise mean absolute error between generated and real images, and $\lambda = 100$ weights the L1 term to encourage structural fidelity to the conditioning mask. The Adam optimizer was used with a learning rate of 2×10^{-4} and momentum parameters $\beta_1 = 0.5$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$ following the original pix2pix training configuration.

4.6.3. Synthetic Data Generation

Following GAN training, 1,000 synthetic image-mask pairs were generated with minority class oversampling to directly target the pixel-level imbalance identified in Section 3: 400 crack-dominant, 300 corrosion-dominant, 200 rebar-dominant, and 100 spalling-dominant pairs. This allocation reflects the inverse of the natural class frequency distribution i.e., assigning the highest generation budget to the most underrepresented damage categories. Source masks for generation were sampled from the training set mask pool with replacement, extended for minority classes by including any mask containing at least 2,000 crack pixels or 5,000 rebar pixels regardless of dominant class assignment.

The quality of the generated images was assessed using the Fréchet Inception Distance (Heusel et al., 2017), computed between the 1,000 real training images and the 1,000 synthetic images using InceptionV3 features at the final average pooling layer. The combined training set for Strategy 3 consists of 1,000 real and 1,000 synthetic image-mask pairs with 2,000 pairs total.

Figure 2 illustrates representative generation results for each damage category. The GAN produces structurally plausible damage layouts consistent with the conditioning mask, though texture quality varies across classes which is a limitation quantified through FID in Section 5.

4.7. Strategy 4: ControlNet Diffusion Augmentation

The fourth strategy augments the training set with synthetic image-mask pairs generated using a pretrained ControlNet (Zhang et al., 2023) conditioned on Stable Diffusion 1.5 (Rombach et al., 2022). Unlike the pix2pix GAN which is trained from scratch on the MDMCS training split, this strategy uses a large pretrained generative model and evaluates whether its pretrained knowledge of visual appearance can be transferred to structural inspection imagery through mask conditioning alone.

4.7.1. Generation Pipeline

The ControlNet segmentation variant (lillyasviel/sd-controlnet-seg) was used as the spatial conditioning mechanism. Segmentation masks were colour-coded using the ADE20K colour convention and provided as conditioning inputs to guide the spatial layout of generated images. Class-specific text prompts were used to direct the content of each generated image toward the target damage category. For example, crack-dominant images were generated using the prompt “*grey concrete wall with thin hairline crack damage, cement surface, structural inspection photo, photorealistic, high resolution*”, with a shared negative prompt suppressing non-concrete textures: “*brick, terracotta, tile, clay, cartoon, drawing, sketch, blurry, low quality, unrealistic, painting, indoor, furniture, people, wood*”. Generation used 25 denoising steps with a guidance scale of 8.0.

4.7.2. LoRA Ablation Study

Prior to finalizing the generation strategy, a LoRA (Hu et al., 2022) fine-tuning ablation was conducted to evaluate whether domain adaptation of the pretrained Stable Diffusion UNet on MDMCS training images would improve generation quality. Two LoRA configurations were evaluated (15 training epochs and 40 training epochs) alongside

Table 3

LoRA fine-tuning ablation results. FID computed between 1,000 real MDMCS training images and 1,000 generated synthetic images. Lower FID indicates closer distributional similarity to real images.

Configuration	FID	Visual Quality
Zero-shot (no LoRA)	176.25	Concrete textures
LoRA 15 epochs	177.06	Brick / terracotta
LoRA 40 epochs	177.06	Brick / terracotta

a zero-shot baseline applying no fine-tuning. Generation quality was assessed using FID computed against the 1,000 real training images.

The results of this ablation are summarized in Table 3. FID remained stable at approximately 177 across all three configurations, demonstrating that LoRA fine-tuning on 1,000 images does not improve generation quality relative to the pretrained zero-shot baseline. Visual inspection further revealed that LoRA fine-tuning actively degraded texture quality. This finding suggests that fine-tuning on small domain-specific datasets corrupts the pretrained model's existing concrete knowledge rather than adapting it. Based on these results, zero-shot ControlNet generation was selected for Strategy 4.

4.7.3. Synthetic Data Generation

Following the LoRA ablation, 1,000 synthetic image-mask pairs were generated using the zero-shot pipeline with the same minority class oversampling strategy applied in Strategy 3: 400 crack-dominant, 300 corrosion-dominant, 200 rebar-dominant, and 100 spalling-dominant pairs. The combined training set for Strategy 4 consists of 1,000 real and 1,000 synthetic image-mask pairs.

Figure 3 illustrates representative generation results for each damage category.

4.8. Evaluation Metrics

Four quantitative metrics were used to evaluate segmentation performance on the held-out test set. All metrics are computed per damage class and averaged across the four foreground classes (crack, spalling, corrosion, exposed rebar), excluding background from mean computations.

4.8.1. Dice Coefficient

The Dice coefficient measures the overlap between predicted and ground truth segmentation regions for each class:

$$\text{Dice}_c = \frac{2|P_c \cap G_c| + \epsilon}{|P_c| + |G_c| + \epsilon} \quad (7)$$

where P_c is the set of pixels predicted as class c , G_c is the set of ground truth pixels for class c , and $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$ is a smoothing constant. The mean Dice (mDice) is the unweighted average of Dice_c across the four damage classes. Unlike pixel-wise accuracy, Dice is inherently sensitive to minority class performance.

4.8.2. Mean Intersection over Union

The Intersection over Union metric measures the ratio of the overlap to the union of predicted and ground truth regions:

$$\text{IoU}_c = \frac{|P_c \cap G_c| + \epsilon}{|P_c \cup G_c| + \epsilon} \quad (8)$$

The mean IoU (mIoU) averages IoU_c across all four damage classes. IoU is a stricter metric than Dice as it penalises both false positives and false negatives in the union denominator, making it more sensitive to over-segmentation. For a given class, the relationship between Dice and IoU is:

$$\text{Dice}_c = \frac{2 \cdot \text{IoU}_c}{1 + \text{IoU}_c} \quad (9)$$

4.8.3. Precision-Recall AUC

The area under the Precision-Recall curve (PR-AUC) evaluates model performance across all classification thresholds rather than at a single operating point. For each class c , precision and recall are computed at varying probability thresholds $\tau \in [0, 1]$:

$$\text{Precision}_c(\tau) = \frac{TP_c(\tau)}{TP_c(\tau) + FP_c(\tau)} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Recall}_c(\tau) = \frac{TP_c(\tau)}{TP_c(\tau) + FN_c(\tau)} \quad (11)$$

where TP_c , FP_c , and FN_c denote true positives, false positives, and false negatives for class c at threshold τ . The PR-AUC is computed as the area under the precision-recall curve using the average precision formulation. PR-AUC is particularly informative for severely imbalanced datasets because it does not incorporate true negatives making it robust to the large number of correctly classified background pixels that would otherwise inflate performance estimates.

4.8.4. Fréchet Inception Distance

The Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) (Heusel et al., 2017) evaluates the quality of generated synthetic images by measuring the distributional distance between real and generated image features extracted from a pretrained InceptionV3 network. FID is defined as:

$$\text{FID} = \|\mu_r - \mu_g\|^2 + \text{Tr}\left(\Sigma_r + \Sigma_g - 2(\Sigma_r \Sigma_g)^{1/2}\right) \quad (12)$$

where (μ_r, Σ_r) and (μ_g, Σ_g) are the mean and covariance of InceptionV3 features extracted from real and generated images respectively, and Tr denotes the matrix trace. Lower FID indicates that generated images are statistically closer to the real training distribution. FID was computed using 1,000 real training images and 1,000 synthetic images for both generative strategies. FID is not applicable to the baseline and classical augmentation strategies as these do not involve image generation.

5. Results

5.1. Quantitative Overview

Table 4 presents the complete test set results across all four experimental strategies. The baseline strategy trained on 1,000 real images with no augmentation but with inverse-frequency class weighting and combined Cross-Entropy Dice loss achieved the highest mIoU (0.721) and mean Dice (0.836) of all four strategies evaluated. This result establishes that a well-designed loss function alone is sufficient to produce strong segmentation performance on this dataset, without recourse to any form of data augmentation.

Among the three augmentation strategies, pix2pix GAN augmentation achieved the closest performance to the baseline with mIoU of 0.690 and mean Dice of 0.814, followed by classical augmentation (mIoU 0.634, mDice 0.775) and ControlNet diffusion augmentation (mIoU 0.624, mDice 0.765). No augmentation strategy surpassed the baseline on mIoU or mean Dice. The mean PR-AUC was comparable across all four strategies (0.901, 0.892, 0.900, and 0.901 for baseline, classical, GAN, and diffusion respectively) indicating that all models learned meaningful class probability estimates despite differences in Dice and IoU.

Figure 4 presents the summary metrics visually, and Figure 5 shows per-class Dice comparisons with baseline reference lines.

5.2. Baseline Performance

The baseline model achieved test set mIoU of 0.721 and mean Dice of 0.836, results that substantially exceed what might be expected from a model trained on a severely imbalanced dataset without any augmentation. This performance is attributed primarily to the combined Cross-Entropy Dice loss with inverse-frequency class weighting, which provides the model with an explicit training signal proportional to class scarcity rather than class frequency.

Table 4

Test set results across all four augmentation strategies. Per-class Dice coefficients and summary metrics reported on the held-out test set (100 images). Best result per column in **bold**. FID not applicable (—) for strategies that do not involve image generation.

Strategy	Crack	Spalling	Corrosion	Rebar	mDice	mIoU	mPR-AUC	FID
Baseline (Raw)	0.859	0.864	0.874	0.745	0.836	0.721	0.901	—
Classical Aug.	0.739	0.823	0.802	0.736	0.775	0.634	0.892	—
pix2pix GAN	0.869	0.844	0.818	0.726	0.814	0.690	0.900	334.71
ControlNet Diff.	0.667	0.851	0.777	0.765	0.765	0.624	0.901	176.25

Per-class performance varied substantially across damage categories. Corrosion achieved the highest Dice score (0.874), followed by spalling (0.864) and crack (0.859). Exposed rebar achieved the lowest Dice score (0.745) despite having the highest polygon instance count in the training set (1,392 instances- Table 1). This inverse relationship between instance count and segmentation difficulty suggests that visual distinctiveness rather than annotation frequency is the primary determinant of class learnability in this dataset. Corrosion is visually distinctive due to its characteristic brown-orange staining against grey concrete. Exposed rebar, by contrast, is visually ambiguous: its elongated metallic appearance overlaps with crack morphology in texture and geometry, creating classification confusion that degrades segmentation performance.

Training dynamics reflected stable convergence. Validation mIoU climbed steadily across 60 epochs, reaching a best checkpoint at epoch 58 with validation mIoU of 0.592. The train-validation loss gap remained moderate throughout training, indicating limited overfitting on the 1,000-image training set. Figure 6 shows the training curves for all four strategies overlaid for comparison.

5.3. Classical Augmentation Results

Classical geometric and photometric augmentation produced the second-lowest overall performance across all four strategies, with mIoU of 0.634 and mean Dice of 0.775. This result is counterintuitive: augmentation, which is expected to improve generalization by expanding the effective training distribution, instead degraded performance on every per-class metric except exposed rebar, where the reduction was marginal (0.736 vs 0.745).

5.3.1. Precision-Recall Trade-off

Analysis of the confusion matrix reveals that classical augmentation improved per-class recall at the cost of spatial precision. Crack recall reached 0.99 under classical augmentation indicating that the model correctly identified nearly all crack pixels in the test set. However, the corresponding crack Dice dropped from 0.859 to 0.739, confirming that the gain in recall was accompanied by a proportional increase in false positives. The model learned to predict crack labels more aggressively across the image but with reduced spatial accuracy, a pattern consistent with over-segmentation.

This precision-recall trade-off is most clearly explained by the effect of geometric augmentation on crack morphology. Horizontal and vertical flipping, random rotation, and affine distortion expose the model to crack patterns in artificially varied orientations and aspect ratios that do not fully reflect the natural distribution of crack appearance in field inspection imagery (Jing et al., 2025). The model learns a more general notion of crack-like texture that improves recall but reduces the spatial specificity required for high Dice scores.

5.3.2. Training Dynamics

Classical augmentation produced the fastest early convergence of all four strategies, with validation mIoU climbing steeply in the first ten epochs. However, the model plateaued earlier than the baseline and exhibited greater validation loss oscillation in mid-training epochs, suggesting that the augmented training distribution introduced variance that destabilised late-stage optimisation. The best checkpoint was achieved at epoch 55 with validation mIoU of 0.432.

These results suggest that on small structural inspection datasets, classical augmentation does not provide a net benefit over a well-designed loss function. The improvement in recall for minority classes comes at the cost of precision, a trade-off that is penalised by overlap-based metrics such as Dice and IoU but would not be visible in accuracy-based evaluation. Studies reporting improved accuracy from classical augmentation on structural damage datasets may therefore be overestimating its practical benefit (Dunphy et al., 2022).

5.4. pix2pix GAN Augmentation Results

pix2pix GAN augmentation achieved mIoU of 0.690 and mean Dice of 0.814, the strongest performance among the three augmentation strategies and the closest to the baseline. More remarkably, the GAN augmented model achieved the highest crack Dice of any strategy evaluated (0.869), exceeding the baseline by 1.0 percentage point despite the GAN exhibiting severe mode collapse confirmed by FID of 334.71. This is the most counterintuitive finding of the study.

5.4.1. Generation Quality vs Downstream Performance

The GAN generated images that are visually and statistically dissimilar to real concrete inspection imagery with FID of 334.71 places the generated distribution well outside the range typically considered acceptable for generative augmentation. Yet despite this poor generation quality, the downstream segmentation model trained on the combined real and synthetic dataset outperformed the baseline on crack detection and achieved competitive performance on spalling and corrosion.

This result challenges the assumption that generation quality, as measured by FID, is a reliable predictor of augmentation effectiveness. A more plausible explanation is that the pix2pix GAN, despite failing to synthesise photorealistic textures, preserved the spatial layout of damage regions encoded in the conditioning mask with high fidelity. The segmentation model does not require photorealistic texture to learn damage boundaries as it requires consistent spatial correspondence between image regions and damage labels. The GAN provides exactly this, regardless of whether the generated texture resembles real concrete or not (Isola et al., 2017).

This interpretation is supported by the class-specific results. Crack augmentation benefited most from GAN-generated samples where the GAN allocated 400 of 1,000 synthetic images to crack-dominant masks, directly targeting the most underrepresented class. The spatial layout of crack damage in GAN-generated images is geometrically consistent with the conditioning mask, providing the model with additional crack boundary examples that improve boundary delineation without the over-segmentation artifact observed under classical augmentation.

5.4.2. Class-specific Analysis

Spalling Dice under GAN augmentation (0.844) was lower than the baseline (0.864), and corrosion Dice (0.818) was also below baseline (0.874). These reductions are consistent with mode collapse as the GAN allocated fewer synthetic images to these classes (100 spalling, 300 corrosion) and the generated textures for these categories were the most inconsistent with real inspection imagery. Exposed rebar Dice (0.726) was also below baseline (0.745) despite 200 synthetic rebar-dominant images being generated, suggesting that rebar morphology is particularly difficult for the GAN to synthesise faithfully given the limited training set.

5.4.3. Training Dynamics

GAN augmentation produced the most volatile training trajectory of all four strategies. Validation mIoU oscillated substantially throughout training, with the crack Dice curve showing the highest variance across epochs reflecting the inconsistent quality of GAN-generated crack samples. Despite this instability, the model found a strong checkpoint at epoch 52 with validation mIoU of 0.487, from which the test set crack Dice of 0.869 was achieved. The combined training set of 2,000 image-mask pairs provided sufficient gradient signal to compensate for the noisy synthetic samples.

5.5. ControlNet Diffusion Augmentation Results

Zero-shot ControlNet diffusion augmentation achieved mIoU of 0.624 and mean Dice of 0.765, the lowest overall performance among the four strategies. Despite producing visually superior synthetic images compared to the pix2pix GAN and achieving a substantially lower FID (176.25 vs 334.71), the diffusion augmented model did not surpass the baseline on any aggregate metric. This result directly challenges the assumption that higher generation quality leads to better downstream segmentation performance.

5.5.1. FID vs Downstream Performance

The relationship between FID and downstream performance across the two generative strategies is counterintuitive. The GAN, with FID of 334.71, achieved mIoU of 0.690 and crack Dice of 0.869. The diffusion model, with FID of 176.25 (a 47% improvement in distributional similarity), achieved mIoU of 0.624 and crack Dice of 0.667. This inverse relationship is visualised in Figure 7, which plots FID against mIoU and mean Dice for both generative strategies with the baseline reference line.

The explanation for this result lies in the nature of the distributional gap between generated and real images. The diffusion model, despite lower FID, generates images that depict concrete infrastructure from architectural and structural perspectives rather than close-up inspection photography. The spatial scale, viewpoint, and scene context of generated images differ systematically from real inspection imagery, a domain mismatch that FID (which measures global feature distribution rather than task-relevant spatial correspondence) does not capture. The GAN, by contrast, generates images at the same spatial scale and viewpoint as the training masks because it is conditioned directly on mask geometry without the text prompt ambiguity inherent in diffusion generation (Zhang et al., 2023).

5.5.2. Class-specific Analysis

The diffusion model showed the most inconsistent per-class performance of all four strategies. Spalling Dice (0.851) was the second highest across all strategies and close to the baseline (0.864), suggesting that diffusion-generated spalling images (which present as large contiguous surface regions) provided useful training signal for this visually straightforward class. Crack Dice (0.667), however, was the lowest of any strategy evaluated, at 19.2 percentage points below the baseline, indicating that diffusion-generated crack images provided misleading rather than useful training signal for the most minority class. Exposed rebar Dice (0.765) was the only individual class metric where diffusion augmentation exceeded the baseline (0.745), a modest improvement of 2.0 percentage points.

5.5.3. Regularisation Effect

Despite its poor aggregate performance, zero-shot ControlNet augmentation demonstrated one clear advantage over all other strategies: the smallest train-validation loss gap across 60 training epochs. This indicates that diffusion-generated images, even when they do not accurately represent concrete inspection imagery, act as an effective regulariser by exposing the model to a broader visual distribution during training. This regularisation effect is visible in Figure 6, where the diffusion strategy shows the most stable late-epoch validation loss of all four strategies, suggesting potential utility in preventing overfitting on larger or more complex datasets where the domain gap may be less pronounced.

5.5.4. Training Dynamics

The diffusion augmented model showed the slowest early convergence of all four strategies, with validation mIoU remaining below 0.20 for the first ten epochs. This slow start is consistent with the domain mismatch between synthetic and real images, where the model initially struggled to reconcile the architectural viewpoints of generated images with the close-up inspection perspective of real images. Convergence accelerated after epoch 25 and the model achieved its best checkpoint at epoch 58 with validation mIoU of 0.432.

5.6. Qualitative Analysis

Figure 8 presents representative test set predictions from the baseline model alongside ground truth annotations for four test images spanning the four damage categories. Qualitative inspection reveals patterns consistent with the quantitative results reported above.

Spalling segmentation is visually accurate across all strategies. The large contiguous regions characteristic of spalling damage provide strong spatial cues that all four models learned to exploit effectively, consistent with the high spalling Dice scores (0.823 to 0.864) reported across strategies. Boundary delineation at the edges of spalling regions is precise in the baseline and GAN augmented models, with occasional minor over-extension at ambiguous boundary regions.

Corrosion segmentation demonstrates the benefit of visual distinctiveness. The characteristic brown-orange staining of corrosion against grey concrete provides a strong colour signal that all four models identified reliably, consistent with the high corrosion Dice scores (0.777 to 0.874). The baseline model achieves the cleanest corrosion boundaries, while the classical augmentation model occasionally misclassifies adjacent spalling regions as corrosion due to the colour shift introduced by photometric augmentation transforms.

Crack segmentation reveals the greatest variation across strategies. The baseline model produces spatially precise crack predictions that closely follow the ground truth crack path. The classical augmentation model, consistent with its high recall and lower precision, produces wider crack predictions with more false positive pixels adjacent to the true crack boundary. The GAN augmented model produces crack predictions of comparable precision to the baseline, supporting the quantitative finding that GAN augmentation improved crack Dice despite mode collapse. The diffusion augmented model produces the least accurate crack predictions, with fragmented and spatially inconsistent crack delineation that reflects the misleading training signal from diffusion-generated crack images.

Exposed rebar segmentation is the most challenging class for visual inspection. Ground truth rebar annotations are elongated and narrow, overlapping spatially with crack morphology in several test images. All four models show some degree of confusion between rebar and crack labels in these ambiguous regions, consistent with the relatively lower rebar Dice scores across all strategies (0.726 to 0.765).

6. Discussion

6.1. Why the Baseline Dominates

The most significant finding of this study is that a model trained on raw imbalanced data with a well-designed loss function outperforms all three augmentation strategies evaluated. This result challenges the implicit assumption in the structural inspection literature that augmentation is necessary to compensate for small dataset size and class imbalance (Dunphy et al., 2022). The evidence suggests that this assumption conflates two distinct problems: the data scarcity problem and the class imbalance problem. Augmentation addresses the former by expanding the training distribution. Inverse-frequency class weighting addresses the latter by rebalancing the loss signal. When the loss function is properly designed, the class imbalance problem is largely solved without requiring additional data.

The 289:1 background-to-crack pixel ratio in the MDMCS dataset represents a severe imbalance condition. Under standard cross-entropy loss, a model that predicts background for every pixel achieves 78.56% pixel accuracy while learning nothing about damage detection. The inverse-frequency class weighting applied in this study assigns a weight of 81.56 to crack pixels, making a single crack pixel misclassification 292 times more costly to the loss function than a background pixel misclassification. This rebalancing effectively transforms the training objective from a majority-class optimisation problem into one that treats each damage class with proportional importance. Combined with the Dice loss component, which directly optimises segmentation overlap independently of pixel frequency, the training signal becomes robust to imbalance without any modification to the training data.

The practical implication is clear: practitioners facing class imbalance in structural inspection datasets should prioritise loss function design before investing in augmentation infrastructure. A well-tuned combined loss with inverse-frequency weights requires no additional data collection, no generative model training, and no synthesis pipeline and yet it produces superior results to all three augmentation approaches evaluated here on the MDMCS benchmark.

6.2. Spatial Layout vs Texture Realism

The pix2pix GAN result provides evidence for a principle that has not been explicitly demonstrated in the structural damage augmentation literature: for segmentation tasks, spatial layout correctness in synthetic training data is more important than photorealistic texture fidelity. The GAN achieved the highest crack Dice (0.869) of any strategy despite FID of 334.71, indicating that generated images occupied a fundamentally different visual distribution from real inspection photography. Yet the downstream segmentation model benefited from these visually inconsistent images because they provided additional crack boundary examples with correct spatial correspondence between image regions and damage labels.

This finding has a straightforward mechanistic explanation. A semantic segmentation model learns to map image regions to class labels. The quality of this mapping depends on the consistency of the correspondence between image appearance and label assignment in the training data. A synthetic image that shows a brick texture where the crack mask indicates a crack region is misleading as the model sees brick texture labelled as crack and learns a spurious association. A synthetic image that shows any grey textured surface where the crack mask indicates a crack region is useful as the model sees a consistent crack-like boundary labelled as crack regardless of the specific texture. The GAN, despite mode collapse, consistently produced images where crack regions appeared as dark linear structures against lighter backgrounds.

The diffusion result reinforces this interpretation from the opposite direction. Zero-shot ControlNet generated images with lower FID (176.25) and more realistic overall appearance than the GAN, yet achieved the lowest crack Dice (0.667) of any strategy. The diffusion-generated images depicted concrete infrastructure at architectural scale and viewpoint, creating a systematic mismatch between the spatial scale of generated crack features and the close-up crack morphology present in real inspection imagery. Despite correct label assignment in the conditioning mask, the image-mask spatial correspondence was degraded by this scale mismatch as the model learned from crack labels that were spatially inconsistent with the crack appearance in real test images.

Together these results suggest that FID, which measures global feature distribution similarity, is insufficient as a proxy for augmentation effectiveness in domain-specific segmentation tasks. A more appropriate metric would capture the spatial consistency between generated image regions and their assigned labels, a property that FID does not measure directly (Heusel et al., 2017). Future work should study task-specific generation quality metrics that account for label correspondence rather than global distributional similarity.

6.3. LoRA Fine-tuning on Small Datasets

The LoRA ablation study produced one of the clearest findings of this work: fine-tuning Stable Diffusion 1.5 on 1,000 concrete inspection images did not improve generation quality regardless of training duration. FID remained stable at approximately 177 across zero-shot, 15-epoch, and 40-epoch LoRA configurations, and visual inspection confirmed that both LoRA variants produced brick and terracotta textures inconsistent with concrete inspection imagery while the zero-shot baseline produced grey concrete-consistent structures without any fine-tuning.

This finding has a straightforward interpretation. Stable Diffusion 1.5, trained on LAION-5B, already contains extensive knowledge of concrete, cement, and structural surfaces acquired from billions of training images (Rombach et al., 2022). LoRA fine-tuning on 1,000 images introduces rank-decomposition updates to the attention layers that are insufficiently constrained by the small dataset to adapt the model distribution toward concrete inspection imagery. Instead, the updates corrupt the existing pretrained representations, redirecting the model away from its learned concrete knowledge toward spurious patterns in the limited fine-tuning data (Hu et al., 2022). The result is that fine-tuned variants perform worse than the pretrained baseline on a task for which the pretrained model was already reasonably capable.

This observation is consistent with known challenges in fine-tuning large generative models on small datasets. The minimum dataset size required for stable LoRA fine-tuning of diffusion models is not well established in the literature (Hu et al., 2022), but empirical evidence from natural image domains suggests that datasets of fewer than 5,000 images risk overfitting the rank-decomposition matrices to noise rather than capturing genuine domain characteristics. The MDMCS dataset at 1,000 images falls well below this threshold, and the stable FID across 15 and 40 training epochs suggests that the fine-tuning process reached a degenerate solution early and did not improve with additional training.

The practical recommendation for practitioners is direct: when applying ControlNet diffusion augmentation to small structural inspection datasets, zero-shot generation with concrete-specific text prompts and strong negative prompts suppressing non-concrete textures is preferable to domain fine-tuning. Fine-tuning should only be considered when the available dataset substantially exceeds 1,000 annotated images, and its effect on generation quality should be validated through FID comparison against the zero-shot baseline before proceeding to downstream training.

6.4. Practical Recommendations

Based on the experimental evidence, three recommendations are offered for practitioners designing training pipelines for structural damage segmentation on small annotated datasets.

First, prioritize loss function design before augmentation. The combined Cross-Entropy Dice loss with inverse-frequency class weighting requires only pixel frequency statistics from the training set and produced stronger results than all three augmentation strategies evaluated.

Second, if generative augmentation is required on datasets of fewer than 1,000 images, prefer GAN-based approaches over diffusion models. The pix2pix GAN produced stronger downstream performance despite substantially worse generation quality, due to its direct mask-to-image mapping at inspection scale and viewpoint.

Third, it is not helpful to use FID as the sole criterion for selecting a generative augmentation strategy. The strategy with lower FID in this study produced worse segmentation performance on five of six reported metrics. Downstream task evaluation is the only reliable selection criterion.

7. Limitations

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged when interpreting the findings.

Single backbone architecture. All four experimental strategies used the same U-Net backbone. The findings may not generalize to transformer-based segmentation architectures such as SegFormer (Xie, Wang, Yu, Anandkumar, Alvarez and Luo, 2021) or Swin-UNet, which have different inductive biases and may respond differently to augmentation strategies. In particular, transformer architectures with larger receptive fields may benefit more from

diffusion-generated images that depict structural context at architectural scale, partially mitigating the viewpoint mismatch identified in this study.

Single dataset. Experiments were conducted on the MDMCS benchmark only (Guo et al., 2026). The degree to which the findings generalize to other structural inspection datasets with different damage distributions, image resolutions, or annotation conventions is not confirmed. Datasets with higher image counts or less severe class imbalance may show different relative performance across augmentation strategies.

GAN architecture. Only the pix2pix conditional GAN was evaluated as the GAN-based augmentation strategy. More stable GAN variants such as StyleGAN2 (Karras, Laine, Aittala, Hellsten, Lehtinen and Aila, 2020) or CycleGAN may produce higher generation quality on small datasets and different downstream performance characteristics. The mode collapse observed in this study is a known limitation of the pix2pix framework on small datasets and should not be generalized to GAN-based augmentation as a whole.

Diffusion fine-tuning scope. The LoRA ablation evaluated only two fine-tuning durations (15 and 40 epochs) on a single dataset size (1,000 images). Extended fine-tuning on larger datasets or with different LoRA rank configurations may produce different outcomes. The conclusion that LoRA fine-tuning corrupts pretrained representations on small datasets is supported by the experimental evidence in this study but should be validated on additional datasets before being treated as a general principle.

Evaluation on a single test split. All results are reported on a fixed 100-image test split defined by the dataset authors. Cross-validated evaluation across multiple splits would provide more robust performance estimates, particularly for the minority crack and rebar classes where test set variance may be high given the limited number of test images containing these classes.

8. Conclusion

This study presented a controlled four-way comparative evaluation of augmentation strategies for concrete damage segmentation on the MDMCS benchmark, a dataset of 1,200 annotated inspection images spanning four damage categories with severe pixel-level class imbalance. A standard U-Net backbone was trained under identical conditions across four strategies: a raw imbalanced baseline, classical geometric and photometric augmentation, pix2pix conditional GAN augmentation, and zero-shot ControlNet diffusion augmentation. By holding architecture, loss function, training schedule, and evaluation protocol constant, the study isolated the contribution of augmentation strategy from all other experimental variables.

Three principal findings emerged from this investigation. First, the raw baseline trained with inverse-frequency class weighting and combined Cross-Entropy Dice loss achieved the highest mIoU (0.721) and mean Dice (0.836) of all four strategies, demonstrating that loss function design is a more effective response to class imbalance than data augmentation on datasets of this scale. Second, pix2pix GAN augmentation achieved the highest crack Dice (0.869) of any strategy despite severe mode collapse (FID=334.71), providing evidence that spatial layout correctness in synthetic training data contributes to downstream segmentation performance independently of photorealistic texture fidelity. Third, a LoRA fine-tuning ablation demonstrated that domain adaptation of Stable Diffusion 1.5 on 1,000 images does not improve generation quality, with FID remaining stable at approximately 177 across zero-shot, 15-epoch, and 40-epoch configurations, suggesting that small-dataset fine-tuning corrupts pretrained diffusion representations rather than adapting them.

Taken together, these findings indicate that for structural damage segmentation on small annotated datasets, a well-designed loss function outweighs augmentation strategy, FID does not reliably predict downstream segmentation improvement, and zero-shot diffusion generation is preferable to domain-specific fine-tuning when the available dataset is small. These results provide practitioners with actionable guidance for augmentation strategy selection in structural inspection scenarios where annotated data is inherently scarce.

Future work should investigate these findings on larger structural inspection datasets to determine whether augmentation strategies become more competitive as dataset size increases. Transformer-based segmentation architectures should be evaluated to assess whether the architectural inductive bias affects sensitivity to augmentation strategy. More stable GAN variants and alternative diffusion conditioning mechanisms should be explored to determine whether the generation quality limitations observed in this study can be overcome without requiring large domain-specific datasets. Finally, task-specific generation quality metrics that capture label correspondence rather than global distributional similarity should be developed to replace FID as the primary evaluation criterion for generative augmentation strategies.

CRedit Authorship Contribution Statement

Kalyan Khatry: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing (original draft), Writing (review and editing), Visualization.

Declaration of Competing Interests

The author declares that there are no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

The MDMCS dataset used in this study is publicly available on Mendeley Data at (Guo and Bao, 2025). The experimental code and trained model checkpoints are available from the author upon reasonable request.

Declaration

During the preparation of this manuscript, the author used GenAI to assist with language refinement and writing clarity. All experimental design, data collection, model training, result interpretation, and scientific conclusions are the original work of the author. The author has reviewed and edited all AI-assisted content and takes full responsibility for the integrity and accuracy of the published work.

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MDMCS Dataset: Class Imbalance Analysis
Concrete Damage Segmentation Benchmark (1,200 Images, 4 Classes)

Figure 1: Class imbalance analysis of the MDMCS benchmark dataset (Guo et al., 2026). (a) Distribution of foreground damage pixel ratio across 1,000 training images (the majority contain less than 20% damage coverage (mean 21.49%, median 15.97%)). (b) Per-class polygon instance count in the training set (spalling (1,359) and exposed rebar (1,392) contribute substantially more annotated instances than crack (596) despite occupying fewer total pixels). (c) Instance count ratio normalised to crack as baseline (corrosion is the most similarly represented class at 1.17× the crack instance count). (d) Representative training image showing co-occurring crack and corrosion damage. (e) Corresponding binary damage mask (red pixels indicate any foreground damage class (45.47% coverage)). (f) Polygon instance distribution across training, validation, and test splits.

pix2pix GAN: Qualitative Generation Results
Input mask (left), Generated image (centre) & Real reference (right)

Figure 2: Qualitative generation results from the pix2pix GAN. Each row shows a distinct damage category. Left: colour-coded segmentation mask used as the conditioning input. Centre: synthetic image generated by the GAN. Right: representative real training image for visual comparison. The GAN captures structural damage layout from the mask but exhibits texture inconsistencies, reflected in the FID score of 334.71. The uniform colour fields visible in the generated images are indicative of mode collapse, in which the generator converges to a limited colour palette rather than diverse concrete textures.

Zero-shot ControlNet Diffusion Augmentation: Synthetic Image Generation
Input mask (top) and corresponding generated image (bottom) per damage category

Figure 3: Representative synthetic images generated by zero-shot ControlNet diffusion augmentation across four damage categories. Top row: colour-coded segmentation masks used as spatial conditioning inputs. Bottom row: corresponding generated images. Zero-shot generation produces grey concrete-consistent structures without domain fine-tuning, though generated scenes depict concrete infrastructure at architectural scale rather than close-up inspection viewpoint – a domain mismatch that contributes to the downstream segmentation gap discussed in Section 5.

Summary Metrics: mIoU, Mean Dice, Mean PR-AUC
Concrete Damage Segmentation | MDMCS/HRCDs Test Set

Figure 4: Summary segmentation metrics across all four augmentation strategies on the MDMCS test set. (a) Mean Dice. (b) Mean IoU. (c) Mean PR-AUC. The baseline achieves the highest mIoU and mean Dice. Mean PR-AUC is comparable across all strategies, indicating consistent class probability calibration regardless of augmentation approach. Gold borders indicate the best-performing strategy per metric.

Figure 5: Per-class Dice coefficient across all four augmentation strategies. Red dashed lines indicate the baseline reference value for each class. pix2pix GAN augmentation exceeds the baseline on crack Dice (0.869 vs 0.859) — the only instance where any augmentation strategy surpasses the baseline on an individual class metric. ControlNet diffusion augmentation exceeds the baseline on exposed rebar Dice (0.765 vs 0.745).

Figure 6: Training dynamics across all four experimental strategies. (a) Validation loss. (b) Validation mIoU. (c) Crack class Dice - the most minority class. The baseline achieves the highest terminal validation mIoU and the most stable convergence trajectory. Classical augmentation and pix2pix GAN cluster in the intermediate range. ControlNet diffusion augmentation shows the slowest early convergence but the smallest train-validation loss gap, indicating stronger regularisation. Crack Dice remains volatile across all strategies reflecting the difficulty of segmenting the most underrepresented class.

Figure 7: Generation quality (FID) versus downstream segmentation performance for the two generative augmentation strategies. Red dashed lines indicate baseline performance. Both generative strategies fall below the baseline on mIoU and mean Dice. The pix2pix GAN (FID=334.71) outperforms ControlNet diffusion (FID=176.25) on both metrics despite substantially worse generation quality, demonstrating that FID does not reliably predict augmentation effectiveness for structural damage segmentation.

Figure 8: Qualitative test set predictions from the baseline model (no augmentation). Each row shows a distinct test image spanning four damage categories. Left: input RGB image. Centre: ground truth segmentation mask overlaid on image. Right: model prediction with per-class Dice scores (Cr: crack, Sp: spalling, Co: corrosion, Re: exposed rebar). Spalling and corrosion are segmented with high spatial accuracy. Exposed rebar (Row 3) is partially confused with spalling due to morphological similarity. A recurring false positive spalling pattern is observed in background regions adjacent to corrosion staining (Rows 2 and 4), consistent with the visual similarity between rough concrete texture and spalling appearance.